

THE MAIN THEORIES OF THE PECULIARITIES OF STRESS IN THE TURKIC LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article defines the nature, localization and functions of the Turkic verbal accent, the general patterns of the implementation of prosodic phenomena in the Turkic languages, as well as against the background of the specifics of the Kurrakolpak language. stress systems of other Turkic and non-Turkic languages. Turkish is one of the stable languages.

The problem of stress in the Turkic languages has not yet been solved. The discussion that began at the end of the XIX century about the place and nature of stress in the Turkic languages did not give a positive result. The question remains open now. The opinions of Russian and foreign Turkologists differed not only on the role of stress in the word, but also on the nature and nature of stress. Currently, there are two main theories about the nature and nature of stress in the Turkic languages. The first of them is that the main accent in the Turkic languages is expiratory, which, according to some representatives of this trend, may be accompanied by an increase in tone, i.e. a musical accent. This opinion is shared by the absolute majority of Soviet Turkologists – authors of grammar and special studies on the phonetics of Turkic languages. This group of researchers includes Russian scientists O.Betling and V.Radlov, some former and current foreign Turkologists also belonged to: I.Kunosh, L.Bonelli, K.Nielsen, V.Perle, J.Denis, K.Grenbek, etc.

Each of the representatives of this trend agrees that the main accent in the Turkic languages is expiratory, and has his own point of view on its place in the word. For example, O. Betlingk, V. Radlov, V. Perle and others believed that the main stress falls on the last syllable in the word. I. Kunosh found that in the Turkic language the main stress falls on the first syllable, and the secondary stress falls on the last syllable. K.Nilson and J.Denis believes that the place of the main stress is determined by the type of syllable vi (open and closed) and the quality of the vowel (wide and long or narrow and short), among other things. G The essence of the second theory, led by Collinder, is that in Turkic languages, in particular Turkic, the main thing in a word is not expiratory, but musical stress, and G. Racette emphasizes. The main musical stress falls on the last syllable of the word, and the exhalation falls on the first.

The Turkic languages form a group of closely related languages that differ in common genetic and typological features. "Phonetic adaptations, similar in nature to languages, allow native speakers of Turkic languages to understand each other. However, despite the phonetic

and grammatical structure common to them, there are minor features in individual languages that are distinguished separately during classification. one Kipchak subgroup, along with Karakalpak, includes Kazakh and Nogai languages.

Many Turkologists have noted that in two-syllable words, the vowels in the first syllable are reduced, and narrow vowels are significantly reduced. A major expert and researcher of this language was N.A. A whole chapter of Baskakov's book is devoted to the Karakalpak language accent.

In the Karakalpak language and in the vast majority of stem languages, the stress falls on the last syllable.

Consequently, stress, along with a combination of vowels and consonants, serves as one of the signs that determine the boundary of a word in the general flow of speech." [2,108].

N.A.Baskakov repeats his main thoughts about verbal stress in the Turkic languages. a few exceptions to the stronger accent [2,27] in languages:

- transfer of stress to the first syllable when counting;
- in interrogative pronouns;
- to distinguish words when their homonymy occurs;

- as for phrasal or logical stress in the Turkic languages in words, N.A.Baskakov considers it musical or tonic, serving as a means of logical selection of key words in N.Kononov's sentence [8,24].

The Turkish accent A.M.Shcherbak gives an exhaustive review, and he writes: "the Turkish accent can be considered indisputable that a strong (expiratory), often, but not always, is accompanied by an increase in tone, its distribution by word... phraseology is closely related to intonation. [10, 117]. He also notes that in some cases the last syllable may have an accent. Basically, A.M. Shcherbak is a supporter of the ideas of hard stress on the last syllable.

Stable head stress on the last syllable in favor of S.K. Kenesboev denies the existence of secondary stress: "in two-syllable and three-syllable words, the stress is relatively pronounced, i.e. the main stress is manifested in two-syllable and three-syllable words." [5,80-81].

He believed that in agglutinative languages, agglutination is a way of forming a word and a form by adding affixes to the root (end), so it is not difficult to conclude about the rule according to which the main stress in Karakalpak and other Turkic languages corresponds to the last formal element, that is, with each layering of the affix, the main stress is transferred from the previous syllable to the next.

So, S.K.Kenesboev emphasizes the limiting role of verbal stress. A.Makhmutsov's work is dedicated to the verbal accent in the Uzbek language. He believes that "the accent in the Uzbek language often arises from a combination of tone and intensity." [6,15].

In addition, the author notes that "the stressed syllable differs from the unstressed one primarily by greater force." [9, 1960.49]. The author draws the following conclusion about the role of verbal stress, which dominates in Turkology, namely: in the Uzbek language, the power stress also falls on the last syllable. The emphasis is on the conclusion that stress is achieved not by a separate or two acoustic components, but by a simultaneous increase in all the physical properties of the syllable (intensity, movement and duration of the main tone), but does not emphasize the leading component.

Indicates the presence of a secondary accent in the Uzbek language. "... in polysyllabic words (with four or more syllables) – writes A.Makhmudov, - in addition to the main emphasis on strengthening the stressed vowel at the end of the word, the secondary emphasis is also on strengthening the stress at the end of the word. vowel at the beginning of the word: at the same time, an increase in the intensity of the pre-stressed root syllable corresponds to a low stress. [6,49]. In addition, a certain place in the work is given to the problem of the relationship between primary and secondary stress.

The accent in the Karakalpak language is Q.Ubaydullayev's monograph is devoted to a separate section. [9.99]. He writes that many languages are heavily accented and dynamic. In the Karakalpak language, the accent is connected. In languages with a Connected accent, the stress usually falls on a certain (last) syllable of a word, that is, in his opinion, in the Karakalpak language, the stress is dynamic and stable and falls on the last syllable of a word. He also noted the presence of a musical and secondary accent in the Karakalpak language. A number of cases are given when the stress does not fall on the last syllable. As we can see, his conclusions largely coincide with the conclusions of his predecessors-Turkologists, but the conclusion that the stressed vowel is longer deserves attention and approval. Vowels with heavy stress are pronounced a little longer than unstressed syllables.

Most researchers of the Turkic languages do not deny the existence of verbal stress, and their activities are aimed at finding their place, determining the function and describing the acoustic nature. Attention is also paid to the problem of secondary stress. So, J. Writes orolboev ... in the Turkic languages, a word has not one, but at least two peaks of stress: the main one is the last syllable, the second one is the main one" [1,153].

But J.Aralbayev adds that "the question of the presence of secondary stress in Karakalpak words, its place and nature remains unclear, there is no answer to the question of how important the duration is in the description of the stressed syllable." [1.68]. This statement of his was written earlier by S. Fully corresponds to Kenesbayev's opinion: " in any case, this issue (about secondary stress) requires an objective laboratory study " [5,18].

Scientists see the reasons for such a variety of opinions, first of all, in the insufficient development of the intonation composition of the Karakalpak language, when various syntactic intonations merge with verbal stress. Listing them, the significant intonation is characterized by the strengthening of the last syllable of the phrase. Consequently, fixed stress prevails at the end of the word. Secondly, a characteristic mistake of supporters of heterogeneous and phonemic stress is that they resort to heterogeneous intonations of some homonymous pairs of words, some of which are phrases, and others are a whole phrase containing a command, request, refusal, etc.

Summing up, Junisbekov writes: "in both cases, there is a misconception caused, firstly, by ignorance of the phonetic structure of the Karakalpak language, and secondly, by the complete copying of some phonetic phenomena of other well-studied languages.system. Hence the pronunciation of the accent of the word in the Karakalpak language as an independent existing phenomenon.

References:

1. Aralbaev J. A, Qozoq tilining vokalizmi. - Olma-Ota: Fan, 1970. - 178-yillar.
2. Baskakov N.A. qoraqalpoq tili. Fonetika va morfologiya. M.: SSSR Fanlar akademiyasining nashriyoti, 1952. 2-jild, 4.1. - 544 b.

3. Baskakov N. A. Turkiy tillarni o'rganishga kirish, 1966. - 384.
4. Junisbeko A. Qozoq tilida so'z urg'usi bormi? - Kitobda: Tilning tovush tuzilishi. - M., 1979, 104-108.
5. Kenesboev. S. K. Olma-Ota: KazSSR nashriyoti, 1962 yil
6. Жамолиддинова, М. (2022). Обучение английскому языку посредством современных технологий. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 29,321-324.

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